

THE SPEECH ERRORS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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***Abstract.** This paper provides with the information about speech errors in teaching foreign languages, their types and origin. The study based on the several sources include the information about the speech production model that consist of 4 components which participate in utterance creation and the definitions of morphological, syntactic, lexical and phonological errors are also given in order to allow to examine the origin of mistakes in an utterance. Also, the degree of brain activation and brain's sectors that were used during the speech in native and foreign languages, were established.*

***Keywords.** Speech Production, Error, Utterance, Foreign Language, Native Language, Pronunciation.*

Introduction

Creating well-structured and fluent speech in a foreign language is a complex process that requires comprehensive knowledge and continuous practice. Proficiency in one's native language can facilitate this process, making it easier to develop fluent and expressive foreign language skills. However, errors in speech production remain likely. One common challenge is language interference, where learners instinctively apply the rules of their native language to the foreign language, causing adaptation difficulties.

Levelt's speech production model identifies four key components of utterance creation: 1) conceptualizer, 2) formulator, 3) articulator, and 4) self-monitoring. Errors, defined as incorrect language use leading to misunderstanding, are central to this study, which explores their types, origins, and strategies to prevent them during early stages of second language learning. Today, people aim for flawless speech production in both native and foreign languages, avoiding errors like

repetition and hesitation to produce grammatically, lexically, and semantically accurate utterances. Before discussing the origins of speech errors, it is essential to define what an “error” is.

According to the Collin’s dictionary the error is something you have done which is considered to be incorrect or wrong, or which should not have been done. And the errors in utterance is an incorrect usage of language and the process of assimilation of information by students [Azimov E.G., Shukin A. N,1990:123].

All in all, the good speech is integral part of our life that help us to communicate with others and the developing of speech occurs throughout our life, moreover the proficiency level of native language influences on the level proficiency of foreign language, for example, if the usage of academic words prevails in your speech, it will be easier to use academic style in foreign language.

According to Varaksina V.A., the good and correct speech obeys to the modern language standards and has clarity, accuracy and appropriateness. Correct speech is characterized by absence of redundant elements that create an unreasonable overloaded statement that complicate it’s comprehending. Most people have basic knowledge of foreign language that needs to be developed in order to achieve high level of language proficiency, but speech errors may complicate the learning process. Causes of errors’ appearance attracted some scientists who shed light on this issue. In work of Varaksina V.A. “Foreign student’s speech mistakes and reason of their origin” some types of speech errors were examined.

In a process of learning foreign language, students try to adapt new language to the rules of their native language. This is called “Pressure of language system” in Varaksina’s work. In most cases this method leads to the mistakes during the speech.

The first type of errors is called “Filling in empty cells” – the appearance of error in the process of adaptation to new system.

“Often the system determines the possibility of manifestation, but in the rules of the language this possibility remains unrealized. The student is guided by the requirements of the system, not knowing or forgetting about the existence of any

restrictions. Thus, they are involuntarily filled in “empty cells.” (Varaksina V.A.)

For instance, student wants to transform the word that is exception from singular form to plural. Student forget that certain word is the exception and adds particular suffix to the word, that is a result of speech error called ‘empty cell’. For example: Childrens, instead of children.

The next speech error is called “Choosing a non-normative option from among those offered by the language system”. Simply put, this speech error is related with the grammatical field. If student chooses wrong option for word transformation, it leads to the error utterance.

The last type of speech errors is a set of mistakes that may be produced in utterances, which has the common name ‘Compositional errors’ and it is related with a structure of the speech.

The compositional errors manifest in a deviation of lexical and syntactic compatibility. It could be incorrectly constructed sentences:

- “I happy met my teacher” (Incorrect);
- “I am happy that I met my teacher.”
- Also, pronominal duplication refers to compositional errors:
- “I wanted him, he gives me money” (incorrect)
- “I wanted him to give me money” (correct)

Tautological error is also a segment of compositional mistakes that manifests as a semantic overabundance of text.

For instance:

- “In my opinion, I think it’s a good book”;
- “The party was an unexpected surprise”

The origin of compositional errors related with a poorly developed short-term memory because this part of the brain is responsible for retention of spoken text fragments. Accordingly, the creating of utterance in a foreign language will be much complicated if student has poorly-developed short term memory.

If we talk about the nature of erroneous utterances in a daily life, we shouldn’t

underestimate the role of interactive feedback. The feedback represents the additional information that can help us to pay attention on our mistakes and correct them.

But feedback can be internal and external. The external feedback we can receive from the interlocutor, but the inner feedback we receive from the various components through which our utterance passes.

The “tip-of-the-tongue” phenomenon occurs when one cannot recall a word despite feeling it is imminent. This results from errors in phonological and lexical feedback. According to Gary S. and Jason M., if lemma retrieval is not linked to phonological activation, it may select less common words as easily as common ones, causing difficulty. Phonological feedback resolves this by prioritizing easily producible words, reducing retrieval errors.

For example, you want to name the thing that store a lot of different information ‘encyclopedia’, but we don’t use this word a lot in our daily life and moreover it has similar meaning and pronunciation with another word, phonological system choose word that is easier to pronounce and also suits to the context, so we say the word ‘wikipedia’.

Also ‘the lexical bias effect’ was examined in the work of Gary S. and Jason M. “Speech errors and language production: Neuropsychological and connectionist perspectives” According to Baars, Motley, & MacKay (1975), the lexical bias effect is a result of internal lexical redactor that first off all is responsible for filtering profanity. Speakers correct their mistakes by themselves, simply we have inner monitoring. Despite that fact the lexical redactor works with internal unspoken speech, while the speaker, saying an erroneous statement aloud, can stop and correct the answer. It points that the error should have been detected in the inner speech.

Conclusion. Speech utterances represents the difficult process that passes through several speech modules, beginning with conceptualization and finish in self-monitoring. And in each module, errors may appear and spoil the intent of speaker. The scientist Kormos, created the speech production model based on

Levelt's model, that helps to understand the functioning of every speech production component. There are a variety of speech errors, like errors in usage of idioms, collocation, compositional errors, tautology errors and etcetera, however all these mistakes we can classify on four segments: Morphological error; Syntax error; Lexical error; Phonological error. To minimize errors when learning a foreign language, individuals should first develop strong proficiency in their native language to enhance self-monitoring. Additionally, teaching learners the key differences between their native and foreign languages can reduce mistakes. For example, Russian lacks articles, unlike English.

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